

The Impact of Digital Transformation on People's Satisfaction with Administrative Procedure Reform in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: In the context of Vietnam promoting the development of a digital government, administrative procedure reform is considered a key area to improve governance efficiency and strengthen people's trust. The study aims to analyze the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform. Mixed methods, in which qualitative research plays a key role with the SWOT tool combined with expert interviews and policy analysis, the study also uses secondary data from SIPAS, PAR Index, and national digital transformation reports. The results show that digital transformation has contributed to increasing transparency, reducing time, costs, and improving service attitudes, thereby improving people's satisfaction. However, factors such as unsynchronized infrastructure, limited digital skills, fragmented data, cybersecurity risks, and digital inequality remain significant barriers. On that basis, the study proposes policy strategy groups according to the SWOT matrix (SO, WO, ST, WT) to promote strengths, overcome weaknesses, take advantage of opportunities, and respond to challenges. People's satisfaction is sustainably improved when digital transformation is implemented in an inclusive, synchronous, and people-centered direction.

KEYWORDS: Administrative procedure reform; digital transformation; people's satisfaction; Digital Government; SWOT

1. INTRODUCTION

Public administrative reform in Vietnam has become a key task to improve the effectiveness of state governance, promote socio-economic development, and improve people's lives. An important pillar is administrative procedure reform, which is considered an area directly related to the rights and obligations of citizens. Resolution No. 17/NQ-CP in 2019 on e-Government development towards digital government, digital economy, and digital society, together with the National Digital Transformation Program to 2025, with a vision to 2030, has strongly committed the State to taking people and businesses as the center of reform (The Government, 2019). Improving the quality of public administrative service provision through the application of digital technology has become an important driving force to increase people's satisfaction, while strengthening trust in the government (Van Hoa et al., 2023).

Practice shows that people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform in Vietnam is still uneven among localities and regions. Evaluation indicators, including the Public Administration Reform Index (PAR Index), or the Satisfaction Index of Administrative Services (SIPAS), have recorded many positive signals, but there are still significant gaps between provinces and cities. While large cities such as Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, and Da Nang have achieved high results thanks to good digital infrastructure and a team of formally trained civil servants, in many remote areas or places with a large number of ethnic minorities, the level of satisfaction of the people is still limited (Duyen & Mai, 2024). The reason may come from the difference in socio-economic conditions, staff capacity, digital skills of the people, and the synchronization in the implementation of technological solutions.

Many domestic and foreign studies have approached the issue of citizens' satisfaction with public services from a different perspective. The studies have used survey tools based on the Likert scale and statistical analysis. Popular models such as SERVQUAL, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), or Information System Success Model have been applied to explain factors affecting people's satisfaction. However, most studies only stop at quantifying the level of satisfaction and determining the relationship between certain variables, without going into depth to analyze the specific contextual factors of Vietnam, especially

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in the current period of strong digital transformation. This leads to an important research gap that there should be works that combine qualitative and quantitative methods, to both provide empirical data and deeply analyze the causes, opportunities, and challenges in the process of administrative procedure reform associated with digital transformation (Asgarkhani, 2005).

Based on the requirements, this study chooses a mixed methods approach, emphasizing the qualitative method with SWOT analysis tools combined with expert interviews and policy analysis. Quantitative methods will be used to supplement by exploiting secondary data from official reports such as SIPAS, PAR Index, and basic surveys of some typical target groups. This approach allows for to identification of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges of the digital transformation process in administrative procedure reform, reflecting the level of people's satisfaction in a specific context.

The objective of the study is to clarify the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform in Vietnam. The study not only stops at measuring and describing, but also analyzes the nature of the influencing factors, providing a comprehensive view of the relationship between digital transformation and the quality of public administrative services. From these analyses, the study will make policy suggestions to improve the effectiveness of administrative reform in the digital transformation period, ensuring the goal of building a digital government for people and businesses (Ginting & Sembiring, 2025).

The study aims to provide a comprehensive perspective, linking theory and practice, quantitative and qualitative. The study adds evidence on the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction in the public administration sector in the context of a developing country. In terms of practice, the study provides specific recommendations to help authorities at all levels adjust policies, improve the capacity to deploy online public services, and support people to adapt to changes brought about by digital transformation. The study contributes to strengthening the role of people as the center of administrative reform, promoting the modernization of public administration in Vietnam in the new period.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS AND RESEARCH OVERVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Basis of Digital Government and People's Satisfaction

In the context of globalization and the strong development of information and communication technology, the concept of Digital Government is replacing the traditional e-Government model. E-Government focuses on digitizing administrative processes to improve transparency and efficiency (Al-Okaily et al., 2025). Digital Government aims at a smart state governance model, taking data as the foundation, citizens and businesses as the center, and opening up new spaces for participation, interaction, and co-creation of policies. In Vietnam, Resolution No. 17/NQ-CP (2019) and the National Digital Transformation Program (2020) have shaped the vision of building a digital government, a digital economy, and a digital society, in which administrative procedure reform is considered a "breakthrough" to improve service quality and people's satisfaction.

People's satisfaction in the public administration sector is defined as the extent to which citizens' expectations of the public services they receive are met, both in terms of content (quality, accuracy, transparency) and process (time, cost, service attitude). Parasuraman's (1988) SERVQUAL theory states that satisfaction is influenced by five aspects, including reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles (Parasuraman et al., 1988). When applied to online public administrative services, these factors are closely linked to the level of development of Digital Government, such as system capacity, security, transparency, and equal access for all subjects (Wang & Ma, 2022).

In addition, the TAM model emphasizes that people's acceptance of technology depends on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. In administrative procedure reform associated with digital transformation, if the online public service platform is designed to be user-friendly, easy to access, and bring practical benefits, people's satisfaction will increase significantly.

2.2. Digital Government Framework and Role in Administrative Procedure Reform

The Digital Government framework in Vietnam is designed on four pillars, including (i) digital infrastructure; (ii) digital platform; (iii) digital data; and (iv) digital human resources. In administrative procedure reform, these four pillars are closely related to each other and directly impact the experience of people. Digital infrastructure includes telecommunications networks, internet lines, and data centers, which are necessary conditions for providing online public services (Christensen & Læg Reid, 2013). Digital platforms are demonstrated through the National Public Service Portal system, an electronic one-stop shop, document management, and administration systems. Digital data plays a core role in connecting and sharing information between agencies, limiting the situation of "asking-giving" and cumbersome paperwork. Digital human resources are the decisive factor in the ability to effectively operate the system, including civil servants and people's digital skills (Tan & Pan, 2003).

People's satisfaction depends largely on the level of synchronous development of these four pillars. If one of the four factors is limited, the entire digital transformation process in administrative procedure reform will be affected, leading to a decline in trust and satisfaction (Yusuf et al., 2023).

Figure 1. The impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform

Figure 1 illustrates the framework for analyzing the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform. The input factors of digital transformation include infrastructure, platforms, data, and digital human resources, facilitating the process of administrative procedure reform through process restructuring, information transparency, cost reduction, and improved service attitude. The result is an increase in people's satisfaction, reflected in convenience, transparency, trust, and confidence in the government.

2.3. Research Overview

Many international studies have shown that Digital Government has the potential to improve the efficiency of public services, facilitate equitable access for citizens, reduce costs, and increase transparency. A typical case is China, where Digital Government has enabled citizens to perform most administrative services online, from tax declaration, business registration, to healthcare, education, and has achieved very high levels of satisfaction. South Korea and Singapore are also successful models in linking Digital Government with citizen satisfaction.

In Vietnam, many studies have evaluated the SIPAS satisfaction index and PAR Index as tools to measure the effectiveness of administrative reform. Some studies have used the SERVQUAL model or observed variables to analyze factors affecting satisfaction (time, cost, staff attitude, transparency). However, few studies have analyzed in depth using the SWOT tool to systematically identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges in the digital transformation process of Vietnam's administrative system.

Integrating SWOT (Strengths - Weaknesses - Opportunities - Threats) into the study of administrative procedure reform associated with digital transformation is important. SWOT is a strategic management tool in enterprises, and is also suitable for analyzing public policies when it is necessary to comprehensively evaluate both endogenous factors (Strengths - Weaknesses) and exogenous factors (Opportunities - Threats).

Strengths are that Vietnam has a stable political foundation, a strong commitment of the Government to digital transformation; the national public service portal system has been operating with thousands of online procedures. Weaknesses are the difference in infrastructure and digital skills between localities; data is not synchronized; several civil servants are limited in applying technology.

Opportunities are the trend of technology globalization, support from international organizations, and the aspiration to build a digital government in Vietnam, the increasing demand of people and businesses for online public services. Threats are the risk of digital inequality, information insecurity, and resistance to change from a group of officials and people accustomed to traditional procedures.

SWOT analysis allows research to more clearly identify the impact of digital transformation on satisfaction, not only stopping at quantitative numbers but also explaining the context, underlying causes, and future development trends.

There have been many studies on people's satisfaction with public administrative services in Vietnam, but most of them only approach quantitatively, lacking in-depth analysis of policies and context. The research gap is that there are not many works that combine the Digital Government framework with SWOT analysis to comprehensively explain the impact of digital transformation on satisfaction.

This study chooses a mixed approach, in which qualitative methods (SWOT, expert interviews, policy analysis) play a leading role, supplemented by secondary quantitative data. This approach reflects the practice of implementing administrative reform in Vietnam in the context of digital transformation.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study was designed using mixed methods to take advantage of the advantages of qualitative and quantitative research, ensuring comprehensiveness in analyzing the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform in Vietnam. Qualitative research plays a key role in exploring in-depth contextual factors, causes, and trends, while quantitative research is used as a supplement to provide an empirical basis and verify the analysis results.

The study analyzed secondary documents including documents of the Communist Party of Vietnam, the Government, reports of the Ministry of Home Affairs, the Ministry of Science and Technology, related studies, and semi-structured interviews with 20 experts, including state management officials at the ministerial and local levels, researchers in the field of public administration,

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and some people's representatives who have practical experience with online public services. The interview questions were structured in an open-ended manner, revolving around four main groups of SWOT factors in the process of implementing administrative reform associated with digital transformation. The interview data were coded and processed using the thematic analysis method, thereby drawing out important arguments.

The study exploited secondary data from existing indexes, including the Satisfaction Index of Administrative Services (SIPAS) and the Administrative Reform Index (PAR Index), and reports on national digital transformation in the period 2019–2024. These data were used to illustrate trends, compare with qualitative results, and provide a basis for determining people's satisfaction levels by region and field.

Combining these two data sources helps the study to have both breadth (quantitative data) and depth (qualitative analysis using SWOT). The study described the impact of digital transformation, explained the causes of differences, and identified opportunities and challenges for the administrative procedure reform process in Vietnam.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Based on the analysis of qualitative data from expert interviews, policy analysis combined with secondary data (SIPAS, PAR Index, national digital transformation report), the study clearly identified the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges in the process of digital transformation's impact on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform in Vietnam.

4.1. Strengths

The political commitment and clear strategic direction of the Vietnamese Government are outstanding strengths. Resolution No. 17/NQ-CP (2019) and the National Digital Transformation Program to 2025, with a vision to 2030, have identified the goal of taking people as the center, considering satisfaction as an important measure of administrative procedure reform. According to the interviewed experts, it was affirmed that stable political factors and strong leadership from high levels are important foundations to promote the implementation process.

The legal and institutional infrastructure for administrative reform and digital transformation is increasingly complete. Vietnam has issued many legal documents on the application of information technology, online public services, personal information security, and regulations on the responsibilities of administrative agencies in service provision. This helps shape the legal framework for the process of digitizing public services, while creating trust for people in using online services.

The online public service system and the national public service portal have been widely deployed. By the end of 2024, the National Public Service Portal had integrated more than 4,400 administrative procedures, of which many essential services, such as birth registration, passport issuance, tax payment, and social insurance, could be performed online. The rate of online settlement of records has increased steadily over the years, contributing to reducing time and costs for people. This is one of the most obvious achievements, recognized by people and businesses.

Improving transparency and reducing administrative hassles. The application of technology, the process of processing documents is more public and transparent, limiting the situation of "asking-giving" or unofficial costs. Some experts have said that the application of the electronic one-stop system has fundamentally changed the way people are served, helping to increase fairness and improve trust in public agencies.

Positive changes in the service attitude of officials and civil servants when implementing online public services. The results of expert interviews show that many young officials quickly adapt to the digital environment, proactively guiding people to use the service. This contributes significantly to increasing satisfaction, especially in localities including Da Nang, Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, and Can Tho. These strengths have affirmed that Vietnam has achieved significant achievements in the process of digital transformation of public administration, creating an important foundation to improve people's satisfaction.

4.2. Weaknesses

The study pointed out many weaknesses that affect people's satisfaction. Digital infrastructure is not yet synchronized between localities. In large cities, people can easily access the internet and online public services; on the contrary, in many rural and mountainous areas, telecommunications infrastructure is limited, and internet speed is slow, making it difficult to perform online services. An interviewed official in An Giang shared that many remote communes do not have stable transmission lines, leading to the situation where people still have to submit applications directly.

People's digital skills are still limited. The elderly, workers with little exposure to technology, and ethnic minorities have difficulty operating on the online public service portal. According to SIPAS 2023 data, over 30% of people still choose to submit applications directly instead of online, reflecting the low level of technology acceptance.

Digital data is fragmented and lacks connectivity. Many specialized databases have not been fully integrated, leading to the situation where people still have to resubmit many types of documents when carrying out procedures. This is time-consuming and reduces people's experience. Experts emphasize that the slow implementation of the national population database and interconnection has slowed down the process of digitizing administrative procedures.

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The capacity and uniformity of the civil servant team are still limited. While several young, dynamic, and responsive officials are quick to adapt to technology, some officials are still hesitant and lack digital skills, leading to low service efficiency. Some cases still show signs of "formal digital administration", that is, digitizing the process but still maintaining manual methods, making people not clearly feel the change.

The issue of personal data security and confidentiality has not been thoroughly resolved. People are still concerned about the risk of information leakage when using online public services. Recent cybersecurity breaches have increased concerns. These weaknesses show that the digital transformation of public administration in Vietnam still faces many barriers, directly affecting people's satisfaction.

4.3. Opportunities

Vietnam currently has many favorable opportunities to promote digital transformation and improve people's satisfaction. Support from national strategies and programs. The National Digital Transformation Program, the Digital Government Development Strategy, and Government Resolutions have created a legal corridor and long-term strategic orientation. This ensures continuity and consistency in implementing administrative reform.

The trend of technology globalization and international cooperation opens up many opportunities to learn from experience. Vietnam can adopt successful models from China, Korea, and Singapore to apply appropriately to the domestic context. International organizations such as UNDP, WB, and ADB are supporting many administrative reform projects associated with digital transformation, creating conditions for Vietnam to improve its governance capacity.

The increasing demand of people and businesses for online public services. People want fast, transparent, cost-saving services; businesses expect convenient administrative procedures, reducing legal risks. Pressure from society will push the government to improve service quality, thereby increasing satisfaction.

Potential from the young population and high internet usage rate. Vietnam has more than 70% of the population using the internet, and more than 90% of adults own smartphones. This is a great opportunity to deploy online public services on mobile platforms, taking advantage of people's familiarity with digital technology.

The development of the digital economy and digital platforms in society. The increasing familiarity of people with online transactions in e-commerce, banking, healthcare, and education will facilitate the acceptance and use of online public administrative services. Thus, the domestic and international context creates opportunities for Vietnam to strongly promote administrative reform in the digital age, aiming at people's satisfaction.

4.4. Threats

The digital transformation process also faces many challenges. The risk of digital inequality, the gap between urban and rural areas, and between the well-off and disadvantaged groups may increase. Without timely support solutions, a segment of the population will be "left behind" in the digital transformation process, thereby reducing satisfaction and trust in the government.

Cybersecurity and personal information security risks. Cyber attacks targeting national data systems can undermine people's trust. Concerns about the disclosure of sensitive information are a major barrier to encouraging the use of online public services.

Resistance to change from a segment of officials and people. Some civil servants are not ready to change their manual working habits; a segment of people still want to submit documents directly to "meet officials". This can hinder the speed of digital transformation and reduce the effectiveness of administrative procedure reform.

Lack of inter-sectoral coordination and data connectivity. In practice, ministries and branches still have a situation of "data isolation", making it difficult to connect and share information. Therefore, people still have to declare many times, which affects satisfaction.

Pressure on financial and human resources, digital transformation requires large investments in technology infrastructure and human resource training. Many localities are difficult areas, do not have enough resources for synchronous implementation, creating an imbalance in administrative procedure reform nationwide. These challenges require the Government to have a long-term strategy and timely solutions to minimize risks, ensure the process of digital transformation of public administration is sustainable, and bring real satisfaction to the people.

The research results show that digital transformation has a positive impact on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform, but this impact is uneven and strongly influenced by the context. Strengths and opportunities demonstrate Vietnam's great potential in building a digital government; meanwhile, weaknesses and challenges reflect the barriers that need to be overcome so that people's satisfaction increases not only at the formal level, but is truly sustainable and profound.

5. DISCUSSION

The research results show that digital transformation in Vietnam has created a clear impact on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform, with many outstanding strengths and opportunities, while also revealing significant limitations and challenges. Comparing these findings with international research helps to clarify the specificities of Vietnam, while pointing out similarities and differences in the process of building a digital government (Hai, 2026).

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In terms of strengths, Vietnam has similarities with leading countries such as South Korea and Singapore in having strong political commitment and a clear strategic framework. International studies confirm that leadership and commitment from the highest level play a decisive role in the success of digital government. The Korean government considers digital transformation as a national strategy, integrating data and services in a unified ecosystem, creating a high level of satisfaction for the people. Vietnam has followed this direction through Resolution 17/NQ-CP and the National Digital Transformation Program, showing the integration of strategic thinking with global trends.

In terms of weaknesses, research in Vietnam clearly reflects the digital inequality between regions, which has been noted in international studies in developing countries. However, compared to China or South Korea, where digital infrastructure is comprehensive and synchronized, Vietnam still has a large gap in telecommunications infrastructure and technical capacity at the local level. Some international experts believe that this is a characteristic of countries with strong regional differentiation, in which the government needs a “digital inclusion” strategy to not leave behind disadvantaged groups (Fleischer & Wanckel, 2024).

In terms of opportunities, research results in Vietnam show the increasing demand of people and businesses for online public services. This is similar to developed countries, where digital government is promoted not only by the government but also by social demand for fast, transparent, and convenient services (Gong et al., 2020). However, unlike Singapore, where people are almost forced to use online services thanks to synchronous policies, in Vietnam, the rate of people choosing to submit applications directly is still quite high. This difference highlights the role of administrative culture and social habits in determining satisfaction levels.

Regarding challenges, Vietnam shares common concerns with countries around the world, such as cybersecurity and personal data security. Studies in the EU show that concerns about privacy and data security are among the biggest barriers to citizens using online public services. In Vietnam, this challenge becomes more evident when the legal framework on personal data protection is newly issued and needs time to be effectively implemented. In addition, the resistance to change by a part of officials and citizens is a problem not only in Vietnam, but also in many countries transitioning from traditional to digital administration.

The discussion shows that Vietnam is on the right track in the digital transformation process, but needs to pay special attention to digital inclusion and digital trust. Without solutions to narrow regional gaps and strengthen people's trust, the positive impact on satisfaction may be limited. Compared to developed countries, Vietnam should make efforts in data connectivity, digital skills training, and information security (Febiri et al., 2024).

The study confirms that people's satisfaction comes from technology factors, service attitude, and the capacity of civil servants. This is in common with international studies, where many studies emphasize that digital government is successful when combining technology, institutions, and people. Vietnam should put two parallel tasks: modernizing technology infrastructure and fostering skills and public service ethics for administrative staff (Hur et al., 2019).

The study emphasizes the importance of increasing people's participation in the digital transformation process. International experience shows that when citizens are more involved in the service co-creation process, satisfaction will be higher. In Vietnam, this can be done through expanding online feedback channels, regular surveys on service experiences, and transparency of reform results.

6. POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The SWOT analysis results have shown that the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction in administrative procedure reform in Vietnam contains many advantages and opportunities, but also contains potential limitations and challenges. To take advantage of strengths, overcome weaknesses, exploit opportunities, and respond to challenges, it is necessary to build a system of policy solutions in an integrated and comprehensive direction (Irani et al., 2023). The SWOT matrix approach provides a useful analytical framework to identify four groups of strategies, including promoting strengths to take advantage of opportunities; overcoming weaknesses by taking advantage of opportunities; using strengths to deal with challenges; and limiting weaknesses to minimize the impact of challenges (Samaratunge et al., 2008).

6.1. Strategy to Promote Strengths to Take Advantage of Opportunities (SO)

Vietnam possesses important strengths such as strong political commitment, a clear legal framework, the operation of the national public service portal, and positive changes in the service attitude of civil servants. At the same time, opportunities come from national digital transformation programs, global trends, increasing people's needs, and the strong development of mobile internet infrastructure.

Policy solutions in this group include expanding the scope and quality of online public services, prioritizing deeper integration of services with high frequency of use, such as health, education, social insurance, and land. This both promotes existing infrastructure and meets the urgent needs of people (Phuyal, 2024). Promote comprehensive digitalization of administrative procedures, not only stopping at digitalizing records, but also restructuring the process, eliminating cumbersome procedures, and ensuring a complete online experience.

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Taking advantage of the young population and high internet usage rate, implementing programs to encourage young people to become "community digital ambassadors", and guiding disadvantaged groups to use online public services. Take advantage of international cooperation, learn from the experiences of leading countries (Korea, Singapore), and at the same time, take advantage of capital and technical support from international organizations to improve the quality of public services (Kim, 2000).

6.2. Strategy to Overcome Weaknesses by Taking Advantage of Opportunities (WO)

Vietnam's weaknesses are the disparity in digital infrastructure between regions, limited digital skills of people, scattered data, and uneven staff capacity. Meanwhile, opportunities from national digital transformation programs and the development of a digital society can be exploited to overcome these limitations (Kim & Han, 2015).

The government should invest in digital infrastructure in remote and isolated areas, allocate budget, and mobilize social resources to ensure telecommunications infrastructure and a stable internet connection in difficult areas, to narrow the digital gap. Strengthen digital skills training for officials and people, organize training courses, community workshops, and integrate digital skills into general education and university programs. For people, there should be a "Digital Citizen Support Center" at the commune level to provide direct support.

Complete the national database and data connection, synchronously deploy the national database on population, land, and social insurance; build a cross-sectoral data sharing platform, and avoid the situation of "data segregation". Promote the participation of digital technology enterprises, encourage enterprises to invest in user-friendly application solutions, and integrate AI and chatbots to support people in using services (Tkachenko et al., 2025).

6.3. Strategy to Use Strengths to Deal with Challenges (ST)

Current challenges include the risk of digital inequality, cybersecurity risks, resistance to change among some officials and people, and a lack of inter-sectoral coordination. Vietnam can take advantage of its existing strengths to respond.

The government should use the electronic one-stop system to reduce digital inequality, deploy online public administrative services in parallel with direct support at the one-stop department, ensuring that vulnerable groups still have access. Strengthen supervision and transparency to create trust, publicize the entire process of processing records, deadlines, and fees/charges on the national public service portal, to limit suspicion from the people (Ioannou et al., 2021).

Apply modern security technology, invest in network security systems, encrypt data, apply international standards on protecting personal information, and improve the incident response capacity of state agencies. Promote political commitment and strong leadership to overcome resistance to change, issue incentive mechanisms, and have sanctions for stagnant officials who do not proactively adapt to new technologies.

6.4. Strategies to Limit Weaknesses to Minimize the Impact of Challenges (WT)

In cases where weaknesses and challenges coexist, there should be a prevention strategy to avoid aggravating existing problems.

Complete the legal framework on cybersecurity and personal data protection, promptly and seriously implement the Decree on personal data protection, clearly defining the responsibilities of public service providers in managing citizen information. Diversify the channels of providing public administrative services, combining online services with support via phone, mobile applications, and hotlines, helping people have more choices and reducing pressure on digital skills (Kim et al., 2022).

Build a close inter-sectoral coordination mechanism, establish an inter-sectoral steering committee at the central and local levels to handle data fragmentation, and ensure connectivity in handling administrative procedures. Ensure sustainable financial resources for digital transformation, supplement the budget, encourage socialized investment in infrastructure, and apply the public-private partnership (PPP) model in the field of online public services. Encourage people and social organizations to reflect and monitor the quality of public services through regular surveys, and apply field reflection applications, thereby creating pressure for continuous improvement (Nana, 2024).

From the SWOT matrix, it is possible to draw some policy directions that should prioritize putting people at the center, improving people's experience, and considering satisfaction as the most important measurement index. Narrow the digital gap between regions, ensuring that vulnerable groups are not left behind. The government should build a legal environment and a reliable security infrastructure so that people can feel secure when using online public services (Srivastava & Teo, 2009). Ensure smooth data and administrative procedures from the central to the local levels, from vertical to horizontal sectors. Link digital transformation with long-term administrative reform, based on technology, institutions, and human resources.

Figure 2. The SWOT matrix and policy orientation

Figure 2 shows the SWOT matrix in the study on the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform. The four main factors include Strengths (S), Weaknesses (W), Opportunities (O), and Threats (T). The study proposes four groups of policy strategies, including SO, WO, ST, and WT, to take advantage of strengths, overcome weaknesses, promote opportunities, and minimize risks. The diagram helps to clearly illustrate the logic from analysis to policy recommendations.

7. CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction with administrative procedure reform in Vietnam in the context of implementing Digital Government. Based on the SWOT analysis framework, the results show that digital transformation brings many important strengths and opportunities, but at the same time, it also reveals weaknesses and challenges that need to be identified and addressed promptly.

Vietnam has advantages from political commitment, a relatively complete legal framework, and an increasingly expanding online public service system. These factors have contributed to improving transparency, reducing processing time, and initially increasing people's satisfaction. In terms of opportunities, the trend of technological globalization, increasing demand from society, and the strong development of mobile internet infrastructure create conditions for administrative reform associated with digital transformation to develop rapidly.

However, the study pointed out many weaknesses, such as unsynchronized infrastructure, limited digital skills of citizens and officials, unconnected data, along with challenges from digital inequality, cybersecurity risks, and resistance to change in public administration. These factors, if not overcome, will reduce the positive impact of digital transformation on people's satisfaction. The study proposed a system of policy implications based on the SWOT matrix, including the SO, WO, ST, and WT strategic groups. The solutions emphasize promoting strengths to exploit opportunities, overcoming weaknesses through leveraging national policies, using strengths to deal with challenges, and limiting weaknesses to minimize risks.

For digital transformation to improve people's satisfaction, Vietnam should approach in an inclusive direction, with digital trust and digital synchronization, putting people at the center of reform. Thus, administrative procedure reform will achieve sustainable effectiveness, contributing to realizing the goal of building a digital government for the people and serving the people.

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